

IUC12: Alignment of application- and higher-level ontologies

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The IUC aims to establish the alignment of application- or domain- level ontologies, developed within the participating research institutions to higher level ontologies, such as the [MatWerk Ontology](#) and the [Basic Formal Ontology \(BFO\)](#). The alignment is crucial to establish the connection and the interoperability between concepts of different domains.

Ontology development support and advisory will be established along with a software interface for ontology alignment.

The application or domain-level ontology which will be aligned to higher level ontologies are selected in respect to their strong domain-and scale overarching representation.

The following participant projects (PPs) are developing application or domain-level ontology with a specific focus:

PP08 Cluster of Excellence Living, Adaptive and Energy-autonomous Materials Systems (EXC 2193-livMatS) is developing an ontology which describes engineered material systems with functions, adopted from living nature. These material systems can have adaptive, energy-autonomous, lifelike properties. As an example, the concept of self-sealing, which is known in plants and transferred to a material system is presented in this ontology.

With this, the ontology is representing interdisciplinary research on energy harvesting and storage, biomimetic, microsystems engineering and soft robotics.

PP05 HoMMage – Hysteresis Design of Magnetic Materials for Efficient Energy Conversion (CRC/TRR 270) will develop an ontology on magnetic materials with the focus on material design and characterization on different scales. The ontology is bridging theoretical and experimental expertise from different disciplines.

PP11 ERC Starting Grant MuDiLingo: Ontology Design for Dislocations (ERC MuDiLingo) is developing an ontology which will describe the physical concept of dislocations in a material, including topology, boundary conditions and interactions. The ontology provides the connection between the material properties and the nature of dislocation and therefore represents scale-overarching concepts.

PP19 and PP20 are not directly developing an ontology but resources, which are required to facilitate ontology development.

PP19 Physikalisch-Technische-Bundesanstalt – Persistent Identifiers (PTB) will provide standards for numerical information, including fundamental, internationally recognized metadata standards and terminology for numerical information and definition of criteria for a formal quality assessment of research data.

PP20 Mat-o-Lab – Materials-open-Laboratory develops an ontology stack for methods and processes.

The ontology development is a connection point to other consortia and different IUCs within NFDI-Matwerk. Particularly, PP08 and PP05 need the description of certain processes (e.g. measurement processes) and are therefore strongly correlating with ontologies in [Platform Material Digital \(PMD\)](#). With the description of defects in a material, PP11 is strongly related to the [IUC04](#) and [IUC17](#) [10.5281/zenodo.12207312.].

The successful ontology development and alignment requires a close collaboration between the researchers and the ontology developers. [The Linked Open Data \(LOD\) working group](#) was established in order to foster information and expertise exchange between ontology developers of different experience and expertise level.

IUC12 started activity in June 2024 and established smaller working groups, which will focus on the ontology development and use the connections to IUC04/17 and PMD.

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